

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A general expression for the statistical error in a diffusion coefficient obtained from a solid-state molecular-dynamics simulation

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Abstract

Analysis of the mean squared displacement of species k , $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$, as a function of simulation time t constitutes a powerful method for extracting, from a molecular-dynamics (MD) simulation, the tracer diffusion coefficient, D_k^* . The statistical error in D_k^* is seldom considered, and when it is done, the error is generally underestimated. In this study, we examined the statistics of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curves generated by solid-state diffusion by means of kinetic Monte Carlo sampling. Our results indicate that the statistical error in D_k^* depends, in a strongly interrelated way, on the simulation time, the cell size, and the number of relevant point defects in the simulation cell. Reducing our results to one key quantity—the number of k particles that have jumped at least once—we derive a closed-form expression for the relative uncertainty in D_k^* . We confirm the accuracy of our expression through comparisons with self-generated MD diffusion data. With the expression, we formulate a set of simple rules that encourage the efficient use of computational resources for MD simulations.

KEYWORDS

diffusion; kinetic Monte Carlo, kMC; mean squared displacement, MSD; molecular dynamics, MD; statistical error

1 | INTRODUCTION

By aiding the interpretation of experimental data, by providing atomic-scale insights, and by predicting data for new systems, molecular-dynamics (MD) simulations are rapidly becoming a key tool in the study of ion transport in solid-state materials.^{1–25} Such simulations yield most easily the tracer diffusivity of species k as a quantitative measure of the ion-transport rate (rather than an ion mobility²⁶ or an Onsager transport coefficient²⁷). Specifically, the tracer diffusion coefficient, D_k^* , is determined from the time evolution of the species' mean squared displacement $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ through the relation

$$D_k^* = \frac{1}{2d} \frac{d\langle r_k^2 \rangle}{dt}, \quad (1)$$

where d is the number of spatial dimensions in which diffusion takes place. This approach presupposes, first, that the MD simulation is run for a sufficiently long time, such that the ballistic regime has already been traversed and the diffusive regime is reached; and second, that gradients in concentration, electric potential, and temperature are absent from the simulation cell. The derivative $d\langle r_k^2 \rangle/dt$ is usually evaluated as the slope obtained from linear regression of the $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ data. From a series of simulations at various temperatures, the activation enthalpy of tracer diffusion, ΔH_D^* , is obtained from an Arrhenius plot ($D_k^* = D_k^{*0} \exp(-\Delta H_D^*/k_B T)$).

Given that diffusion is a stochastic process, D_k^* data obtained from MD simulations will inherently show some statistical scatter. The best

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way to estimate the magnitude of this scatter, strictly speaking, is to perform several simulation runs with different initial conditions,^{28,29} but this is rarely done. In many instances, an estimate of the error in D_k^* is omitted. On occasion, an error is given, but its origin is not always specified. An obvious approach is to use the standard error of the linear regression slope in the $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ plot as a measure of the error. The least-squares criterion used in standard linear regression routines, however, refers to a set of independent data points, whereas each data point in a plot of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ versus t is not independent of the other data points (i.e., $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ data are autocorrelated). Consequently, the regression error will, on principle, severely underestimate the error in D_k^* . In particular, in the case of MD simulations of small simulation cells with short simulated time periods, the regression error may mask a statistically questionable result by incorrectly implying that D_k^* has been obtained with high accuracy.

Two studies in which the error in D_k^* was examined in some detail^{30,31} found empirically that the relative error $u_{\text{rel}}(D_k^*)$ could be described approximately by $(A/\sqrt{t_{\text{sim}}}) + B$, where A and B are fitting constants. To calculate a relative error, the true value of D_k^* is of course required as a reference; but in both cases,^{30,31} true values of D_k^* were not known a priori, and hence, the reference values were taken from the longest MD simulation that could be carried out. A “long” simulation run does not guarantee, however, that the true value of D_k^* is obtained, especially for those simulations employing a small number of mobile particles k or temperatures too low relative to $(\Delta H_{D^*}/k_B)$. A different approach is therefore required, one that does not rely on “long” MD simulations, one that is less empirical and less approximate, and one that yields an expression that takes into account a variety of key factors, not simply the simulation run time.

In this study, we are concerned with $u_{\text{rel}}(D_k^*)$, the relative error in a tracer diffusion coefficient, obtained from $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$, the time evolution of the mean squared displacement of diffusing particles k . We focus on diffusion in a solid by a vacancy mechanism, but the results are also applicable to diffusion by an interstitialcy mechanism. We took the approach of obtaining $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curves from kinetic Monte Carlo (kMC) simulations. The conceptual benefit of this approach is that we avoid relying on data obtained from a “long” simulation run: the input data to the kMC simulations (jump distance, attempt frequency, and height of the jump barrier) automatically provide the reference value of D_k^* (with knowledge of f^* , the tracer correlation coefficient). In addition, there is a practical benefit: since each kMC simulation has a very low computational cost compared to an MD simulation, it is possible to obtain a representative picture of diffusion statistics by carrying out a huge (i.e., statistically relevant) number of simulation runs. Consequently, the uncertainty in a calculated diffusion coefficient can be obtained as a function of simulation run time, simulation cell size, defect concentration, and a barrier-height/temperature factor, for a much larger parameter space than would be feasible through a series of MD simulations. On the basis of such kMC simulations we derive in Section 4 a closed-form expression for $u_{\text{rel}}(D_k^*)$ that captures the key dependences. Subsequently, we use this expression in Section 5 to predict whether an MD simulation will provide data with an uncertainty below a given level. We first test the predictions on MD data

that we generate ourselves, and then, we turn a critical eye to literature data. In both Sections 4 and 5, we discuss how the expression can be used to distribute computational resources so that $D_k^*(T)$ and thus ΔH_{D^*} can be obtained with low uncertainties.

2 | METHODS

For the kMC and MD simulations, we considered oxygen-vacancy diffusion in SrTiO₃, primarily because it is a system that has been extensively studied, so that there is excellent agreement from a variety of methods (chemical diffusion,³² nuclear spin relaxation,³³ tracer diffusion,³⁴ anelastic relaxation,³⁵ and classical MD simulations³⁶) as to the absolute magnitude of the vacancy diffusivity and its activation enthalpy (of 0.62 eV). Furthermore, this value of the migration barrier is also obtained from static supercell simulations based on density-functional-theory (DFT) calculations with sufficiently large cells containing an even number of perovskite formula units in all three spatial dimensions.³⁷ A second reason for taking oxygen-vacancy diffusion in SrTiO₃ as our model system is that the tracer correlation factor is known for this migration mechanism in this structure ($f^* \approx 0.69$),³⁸ allowing D_O^* to be predicted on the basis of the inputs to the kMC simulations (attempt frequency, activation energy, jump distance, and vacancy concentration).

2.1 | kMC simulations

A rejection-free kinetic Monte Carlo (kMC) algorithm (*n-fold way*)³⁹ was implemented in Python, with the help of the NUMPY⁴⁰ and SCIPY⁴¹ frameworks. No interactions between the jumping vacancies or between vacancies and possible foreign atoms were taken into account. Beside our model system, the cubic perovskite SrTiO₃, we also carried out kMC simulations on supercells of the three-dimensional simple cubic (sc), face-centered cubic (fcc), and body-centered cubic (bcc) lattices, and of the two-dimensional square lattice. In the example of SrTiO₃, only the oxygen sublattice of the perovskite structure was included in the simulations.

To achieve comparability of the kMC and MD simulation data for SrTiO₃, we adopted the kinetic parameters $\Delta H_{\text{mig}} = 0.62 \text{ eV}$ and $\nu'_0 = 4.6 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$ of SrTiO₃.³⁶ On this basis, the average jump rate Γ_V was taken to be

$$\Gamma_V = \nu'_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_{\text{mig}}}{k_B T}\right). \quad (2)$$

In the kMC model of SrTiO₃, we adopted the lattice constants a_0 from the MD simulation runs (see Table S2 in Data S1), according approximately to the expression⁴²

$$a_0/\text{\AA} = 3.90 + 6.64 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1} \cdot T. \quad (3)$$

As mentioned before, kMC simulations bear the inherent advantage that, in ideal dilute solutions, the expectation value of the

vacancy diffusion coefficient, D_v , may be calculated directly from the input parameters, thus allowing for a straightforward assessment of the simulation outcome's accuracy. Specifically, for this prediction, the jump rate Γ_v , the coordination number Z within the sublattice, the jump distance s_v , and the dimensionality d of the lattice are necessary:

$$D_v = \frac{Z}{2d} \cdot \Gamma_v \cdot s_v^2. \quad (4)$$

E.g., for the oxygen sublattice of the perovskite structure, $d=3$, $Z=8$, and s_v is given by $s_v = a_0/\sqrt{2}$. From D_v , the tracer diffusion coefficient D_k^* is obtained as

$$D_k^* = f^* \cdot \frac{N_v}{N_k} \cdot D_v, \quad (5)$$

with the number N_v of vacancies and the number N_k of tracer particles on the k sublattice. For the different considered crystal structures, we employed literature values^{38,43,44} of f^* for infinitely large crystals (see Table S1 in Data S1). For supercell sizes of at least $3 \times 3 \times 3$, these ideal values were found to be a reasonable approximation (see Figure S1 in Data S1).

2.2 | MD simulations

The MD simulations were carried out with the LAMMPS code.^{45,46} The long-range coulombic interactions were calculated with a particle-particle/particle-mesh solver⁴⁷ with a relative accuracy of 10^{-5} . Newton's equations of motion were integrated by means of the velocity Verlet algorithm with a timestep of 1 fs. The pair potential set derived by Pedone et al.⁴⁸ was used to describe the interatomic interactions, with the short-range interactions being evaluated up to a cut-off of 12 Å. The simulation cells were created by replicating a single unit cell of SrTiO₃ $N_{\text{cell}} \times N_{\text{cell}} \times N_{\text{cell}}$. Oxygen vacancies were introduced by randomly deleting the required number of oxide ions; the resulting charge imbalance was compensated by slightly lowering the charge of all Ti cations. Every simulation cell was first equilibrated for 100 ps in an isothermal-isobaric (NpT) ensemble that was controlled by a Nosé-Hoover^{49,50} thermostat (barostat) with a damping parameter of 0.1 ps (1.0 ps). It was confirmed that, after the time span of 100 ps, the total energy and volume of the cell were constant (except for small high-frequency fluctuations). The subsequent production run was carried out in the NVT ensemble, with the constant cell volume fixed at the time-averaged volume obtained from the end of the NpT equilibration run.

3 | FUNDAMENTAL PROPERTIES OF $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ CURVES

Before we consider the effects of various simulation parameters on the tracer diffusion coefficient, D_k^* , we first examine some properties

of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curves. In particular, we demonstrate that the commonly used method of calculating $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ by time averaging provides no statistical advantage compared with the approach of calculating $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ with reference to the initial state at time t_0 . In addition, we show that the extraction of D_k^* by least-squares linear regression is no more reliable than obtaining D_k^* from the difference quotient of two data points.

3.1 | The influence of time averaging on the error of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$

Two methods are most commonly used to extract $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ from an MD simulation. Variant A is conceptually the simpler one: it is an ensemble average over the displacements of all particles relative to their positions at time t_0 :

$${}^A\langle r_k^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{j < N_k} \| \mathbf{r}_j(t) - \mathbf{r}_j(t_0) \|^2. \quad (6)$$

Variant B is the ensemble average of a time average. $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ is then a function of a time lag Δt , rather than of the time t itself:

$${}^B\langle r_k^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{j < N_k} \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{t < t_{\text{sim}}} \| \mathbf{r}_j(t + \Delta t) - \mathbf{r}_j(t) \|^2. \quad (7)$$

This variant is commonly used to analyze data from ab-initio MD,^{22,31,51-54} with the aim of reducing the considerable statistical scatter that arises from small particle numbers (cell sizes) and run times. By virtue of providing smooth $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curves, this variant is very useful for the identification of the ballistic regime³¹ and of anomalous diffusion on small time scales.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸ A third variant⁵⁹ is to average over non-overlapping time intervals. This variant is not commonly applied in the literature, and so we do not consider it further here.

From a set of kMC simulations of oxygen diffusion in SrTiO₃, we extracted the two variants of $\langle r_0^2 \rangle$ with Equations (6) and (7). Values of D_0^* were obtained by applying ordinary least-squares linear regression to the ${}^A\langle r_0^2 \rangle(t)$ curves, on the one hand, and weighted least-squares linear regression to the ${}^B\langle r_0^2 \rangle(\Delta t)$ curves, on the other hand (the data points at small Δt being assigned a larger weight according to a $1/\sqrt{\Delta t}$ law⁶⁰). The results for $T=2000\text{K}$ and two different run times are shown in Figure 1. Although the ${}^B\langle r_0^2 \rangle$ data in both cases have a much smoother appearance than the ${}^A\langle r_0^2 \rangle$ data, there is no substantial statistical advantage to Variant B in terms of the error in D_0^* . A reduction of the error in D_0^* may be attained either by truncating the ${}^B\langle r_0^2 \rangle(\Delta t)$ curve at small Δt or by averaging over a number of independent ${}^A\langle r_0^2 \rangle(t)$ curves of a matching length, with both the benefit and the overall simulation time of both approaches being comparable (see Section S4 in Data S1).

These results indicate that the two variants are equivalent with respect to the calculation of the error in D_0^* , but there are some aspects that argue against the use of ${}^B\langle r_k^2 \rangle$: first, because the smoothness of a data set is often (subjectively) considered to indicate a low error, the use of ${}^B\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ suggests a higher (and misleading) degree of

FIGURE 1 (A) and (C) Exemplary $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$ data from a set of kMC simulations of oxygen tracer diffusion in SrTiO₃; (B) and (D) distributions of the calculated tracer diffusion coefficients. $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$ was calculated without and with time averaging (variants A and B, shown as dotted and solid lines, respectively). The three exemplary curves were chosen from a set of 100 kMC runs as those cases exhibiting the minimal, maximal, and average observed diffusion coefficient. The simulations were carried out on a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ SrTiO₃ supercell at $T = 2000\text{K}$; the simulation times were chosen so as to reflect typical time scales of AIMD simulations (A and B) and of classical MD simulations (C and D).

precision. Second, the representation of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ as a function of time lag Δt , rather than time t , may mask methodological errors (such as an insufficient pre-equilibration of the simulation cell). And third, the calculation of ${}^B\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ is computationally more expensive, since the full history of the particles' displacements must be stored, whereas the calculation of ${}^A\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ is readily done on-the-fly, and the displacements may be discarded after each time step.

For these reasons, we maintain that, for the analysis of the diffusive regime of a $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ curve, Variant A is the preferable way to calculate the mean squared displacement. In the following Sections, ${}^A\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ will be employed as the generic way of calculating $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$; it will therefore not be indicated explicitly.

FIGURE 2 (A) Different methods for extracting the diffusion coefficient from $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ curves, comparing least-squares linear regression and the simple difference quotient for an exemplary ${}^A\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$ curve. (B) Distributions of D_O^* values calculated by the different methods from a set of 100 kMC runs of a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ SrTiO₃ supercell at $T = 2000\text{K}$.

3.2 | Extracting the diffusion coefficient: Linear regression versus difference quotient

In view of Equation (1), the use of linear regression to obtain a tracer diffusion coefficient from a $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curve seems a natural choice. But as noted in the Introduction, linear regression assumes a set of independent data points, and this independence is not given within a $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curve. In order to demonstrate this issue, we compute D_k^* using linear regression and, for comparison, using only the very first and the very last point of a $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curve (within, of course, the diffusive regime). That is, we approximate the time derivative of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ by a difference quotient:

$$D_k^* = \frac{1}{2d} \frac{\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t_1) - \langle r_k^2 \rangle(t_0)}{t_1 - t_0}. \quad (8)$$

The results are shown in Figure 2. We see that there is no substantial statistical advantage in calculating D_k^* by means of linear regression over calculating it by a simple difference quotient. We also

see that the regression error, unsurprisingly, fails to capture the statistical scatter of the simulation outcome. Hence, the vast majority of the $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ data (i.e., all data points except the first and the last) do not contribute any information that is relevant for the assessment of the diffusion coefficient. Clearly, the apparent wealth of data in a $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curve is misleading.

4 | ANALYSIS OF THE STATISTICAL ERROR OF D_k^* BY KMC SIMULATIONS

In the vast majority of cases, a value of D_k^* is determined from a single MD run and the statistical uncertainty is not evident. As demonstrated in Section 3, the regression error provides no reliable estimate of the true uncertainty. Although the error in a single MD run can be estimated by rather sophisticated methods, for example, bootstrap resampling,⁶¹ there are two compelling advantages in having a closed-form expression for the relative error in D_k^* . First, calculating the error directly from $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curves is simpler and quicker. Second, directed partitioning of computing time between runs at different temperatures is possible: as we will show, increasing the simulation time may, in some cases, have no benefit, while in others, it may greatly enhance the accuracy. Our approach is, therefore, to derive a closed-form expression based on an extensive set of kMC results.

4.1 | Assessing the errors on activation enthalpy and pre-exponential factor

Calculating $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$, and subsequently D_k^* , as a function of temperature allows the activation enthalpy of tracer diffusion, ΔH_{D^*} , to be obtained from an Arrhenius plot. In general, the quality of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ data in terms of linearity and smoothness (i.e., no curvature and no discontinuities) decreases with decreasing temperature. Eventually, at some low temperature, not even one single tracer particle jump will occur during the entire course of the simulation. This general decrease in data quality presents a problem if the temperature range for which MD simulations yield high-quality data is substantially different to the temperature range of experimental interest (i.e., the range for which experimental data are available or for which predicted data are desired). Values of D_k^* for the lower temperatures must then be estimated by extrapolating the simulated data to the lower temperatures. This approach is physically reasonable, provided that there is no change in diffusion mechanism and no change in point-defect behavior (such as a change from intrinsic to extrinsic defect regimes) between the higher and the lower temperature ranges. Nonetheless, the extrapolated diffusivities may be subject to large uncertainties when the extrapolation is carried out across a large temperature difference. If the extrapolated values cannot be complemented with reliable estimates of these uncertainties, unreliable conclusions may be reached, even if the extrapolation approach is, in principle, valid.

As a first step, we demonstrate the importance of sufficiently large cells and sufficiently long simulation times for the accuracy of

MD simulation results. We determined the statistical distributions of activation enthalpies and pre-exponential factors obtained from an Arrhenius analysis of data from kMC simulations of oxygen diffusion in SrTiO₃. Such simulations were carried out for different simulation cell sizes ($N_{\text{cell}} \times N_{\text{cell}} \times N_{\text{cell}}$) at five temperatures, with 100 runs per (N_{cell}, T) pair. From the resulting set of 100⁵ conceivable distinct Arrhenius plots, a subset of 10⁵ Arrhenius plots was drawn by random sampling.

The results are shown in Figure 3A–D. The scatter in the activation enthalpy of diffusion, ΔH_{D^*} , and in the pre-exponential factor, D^{*0} , are strongly diminished with increasing N_{cell} and are generally much narrower for $t_{\text{sim}} = 1\text{ns}$ than for $t_{\text{sim}} = 100\text{ps}$. While this is hardly surprising, it is striking that values of ΔH_{D^*} twice as high as the reference value are possible for small N_{cell} and short t_{sim} , albeit with low probability. In Figure 3E,F we plot the probability of obtaining a given activation enthalpy if only one set of simulations (i.e., one run per temperature) was performed. These plots show that, in the case of the $3 \times 3 \times 3$ supercell, for example, almost 20% of the extracted values of ΔH_{D^*} deviate by 20% or more from the true value of 0.62eV, while for $t_{\text{sim}} = 1\text{ns}$, the corresponding percentage (of values that deviate by 20% or more) is smaller than 0.4%. The major consequence is that the extrapolation to a lower temperature is considerably less reliable for the smaller simulation cells and for the shorter simulation runs. Taking a target temperature of $T = 400\text{K}$, so that the extrapolated temperature is substantially lower than the lowest temperature examined in the simulations ($T = 1200\text{K}$), we find in Figure 3G,H, that for the $3 \times 3 \times 3$ cell and $t_{\text{sim}} = 100\text{ps}$, 99% of the extrapolated values of D_k^* span over almost six orders of magnitude (with the majority of values being well below the reference value), compared with about two orders of magnitude for the same cell with $t_{\text{sim}} = 1\text{ns}$ (with a substantial proportion around the reference value). It is stressed that the quantitative results of Figure 3 are specific to oxygen diffusion in SrTiO₃ and the temperature range considered. A higher set of temperatures, or a material with a lower activation barrier, will produce different quantitative results, on account of the higher jump rates, but the same qualitative results. The main purpose of Figure 3 is thus a qualitative illustration.

The results of Figure 3 also indicate that larger cells with a higher number of vacancies yield more accurate results than the smaller cells. This trend is especially strong for the longer simulations: as an example, the portion of ΔH_{D^*} values within $\pm 2\%$ accuracy increases from 23% to 88% upon an increase from a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ to a $20 \times 20 \times 20$ supercell size.

While the results for $t_{\text{sim}} = 1\text{ns}$ indicate the advantage of increasing the cell size, this trend is not as clear for the shorter simulations. In that case, there appears to be a sudden enhancement at $N_{\text{cell}} = 10$ (Figure 3E), which suggests that the improvement might be due entirely to the increase in the number of vacancies, rather than the increase in cell size. In the following, we examine the extent to which larger cell sizes or higher numbers of vacancies contribute to the enhanced accuracy of the simulation outcome. Our overarching aim is to generalize the results so that they apply quantitatively to all systems, not just to oxygen diffusion in SrTiO₃.

FIGURE 3 Distributions of (A, B) the activation enthalpy of diffusion, ΔH_{D^*} , and (C, D) the normalized pre-exponential factor, $D_0^{*0} \cdot N_v^{-1} N_0$. ΔH_{D^*} and D_0^{*0} were calculated from Arrhenius plots of D_0^* obtained by means of kMC simulations of $N_{cell} \times N_{cell} \times N_{cell}$ SrTiO₃ supercells. Simulations were run for either $t_{sim} = 100$ ps or $t_{sim} = 1$ ns at $T/K = \{1200, 1400, 1600, 1800, 2000\}$. (E, F) show the probability of obtaining, from a single Arrhenius plot, a result of ΔH_{D^*} at a given accuracy (lines are guides to the eye). Distributions of D_0^* values obtained by extrapolation to $T = 400$ K are shown in (G, H). The dashed horizontal lines denote the reference values.

4.2 | A systematic examination of the relative error

Having recognized above the benefits of increasing the cell size, the number of vacancies, or the simulation time on the accuracy of the oxygen tracer diffusion coefficient, D_0^* , we investigate now the influence

of these parameters on $u_{rel}(D_0^*)$, the relative error in D_0^* , systematically and quantitatively. To this end, we calculated $u_{rel}(D_0^*)$ from $\langle r_0^2 \rangle$ curves that were sampled by kMC simulations of SrTiO₃ supercells. The relative errors were obtained by normalizing, to the known true value of D_0^* , the empirical standard deviations of the diffusion coefficients from 100 simulation runs for each individual parameter set.

FIGURE 4 Relative error of the oxygen tracer diffusion coefficient, D_{O}^* , extracted from kMC simulations of SrTiO_3 at $T = 2000\text{K}$, as a function of simulation time t_{sim} . Fits of the expression $(A/\sqrt{t_{\text{sim}}}) + B$ are shown as lines. Data were obtained from the standard deviations of 100 kMC runs per data point; the considered supercells contained one oxygen vacancy.

We consider first the behavior of $u_{\text{rel}}(D_{\text{O}}^*)$ as a function of simulation time. The relative error is found in Figure 4 to decrease with increasing t_{sim} for each cell size, before reaching an apparent plateau. With increasing cell size, the plateau value of the relative error shifts to substantially lower values, and the onset of the plateau is shifted to longer simulation times. Also shown in Figure 4 is that, for each individual supercell, the time dependence can be described by an expression of the form $A/\sqrt{t_{\text{sim}}} + B$, as proposed in the literature,^{30,31} albeit with different values of B for each cell size (confirming the conclusion of the earlier study³⁰). In other words, such an expression does not include the influence of the cell size and hence, it will not be able to provide reliable predictions across various simulation cells.

Two further points need to be stressed. First, the results of Figure 4 indicate that, if a simulation with a given t_{sim} falls in the plateau regime, a further increase in simulation time will not reduce the relative error in D_{O}^* . It is then advisable to carry out several independent runs and to average over the values in order to obtain a lower relative error (see Section S4 in Data S1). The key issue, though, is how does one determine whether a single simulation falls in the plateau regime or not? A quantitative expression for $u_{\text{rel}}(D_{\text{O}}^*)$ would make such a determination possible. Second, the time required to reach the plateau regime depends on the jump rate, so that the results of Figure 4 are specific to the oxygen-migration kinetics in SrTiO_3 at $T = 2000\text{K}$ and cannot be applied quantitatively to other temperatures (at given cell size and defect concentration). For example, a simulation time that, by falling within the plateau regime, provided the lowest possible uncertainty for a cell at $T = 2000\text{K}$ may be entirely insufficient at, say, $T = 1500\text{K}$, as the plateau regime has not been reached. In this case, a longer simulation at $T = 1500\text{K}$ would be helpful. That is to say, simulations at lower temperatures may need increasingly longer simulation times to obtain similar $u_{\text{rel}}(D_{\text{O}}^*)$. Again, a quantitative expression would allow such decisions to be made.

Next we consider the behavior of the relative error as a function of cell size. For reasons that will become clear, we plot the relative error in

FIGURE 5 Relative error of the oxygen tracer diffusion coefficient, D_{O}^* , extracted from kMC simulations of SrTiO_3 , as a function of the number N_{O} of oxygen ions in the simulation cell. Fits of the expression $(G/\sqrt{N_{\text{O}}}) + H$ are shown as lines. Data were obtained from the standard deviations of 100 kMC runs per data point; the considered supercells contained one oxygen vacancy.

Figure 5 as a function of N_{O} , the number of oxygen ions in the simulation cell, rather than of N_{cell} itself (in this case, $N_{\text{O}} = 3N_{\text{cell}}^3 - 1$). The relative error is seen to decrease with increasing N_{O} , the decrease being stronger for longer t_{sim} . The relative error appears to reach a plateau at large N_{O} , with the plateau value decreasing with increasing simulation time. Another effect of increasing t_{sim} is a shift of the plateau's onset to larger N_{O} . This behavior, incidentally, is consistent with the results of Figure 3, that the cell-size dependence is much clearer for the simulations with $t_{\text{sim}} = 1\text{ns}$ than for those with $t_{\text{sim}} = 100\text{ps}$. Analogously to the dependence of the relative error on t_{sim} (Figure 4), the dependence on N_{O} may be described rather well with an expression of the form $G/\sqrt{N_{\text{O}}} + H$, with fitting parameters G and H .

In Figure 5 we also show that, with increasing t_{sim} , the dependence of the relative error on N_{O} approaches an inverse-square-root law:

$$u_{\text{rel}} = \frac{u(D_{\text{O}}^*)}{D_{\text{O}}^*} \approx \sqrt{\frac{2}{3 \cdot N_{\text{O}}}}, \quad (9)$$

This dependence takes exactly the same form as that of the relative uncertainty of $\langle r^2 \rangle$ in the continuum limit of an ensemble of N ordinary random walkers (RW) in d spatial dimensions (mathematical derivation see Section S2 in Data S1):

$$u_{\text{rel}}^{\text{RW}} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{d \cdot N}}. \quad (10)$$

We will make use of this expression later. Lastly, the behavior for different numbers of vacancies, N_{v} , is examined in Figure 6. When a larger number of vacancies is present in the simulation cell, the relative errors are generally lower, but this beneficial effect becomes weaker with increasing simulation time, and it appears to vanish in the plateau with respect to t_{sim} . Accordingly, in fits of the expression $A/\sqrt{t_{\text{sim}}} + B$, only a small shift in B is seen, while A is reduced

FIGURE 6 Relative error of the oxygen tracer diffusion coefficient, D_O^* , as a function of simulation time t_{sim} obtained from kMC simulations of a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercell of SrTiO_3 with $N_v = \{1, 4, 16\}$. Fits of the expression $(A/\sqrt{t_{\text{sim}}}) + B$ are shown as lines. Data were obtained from the standard deviations of 100 kMC runs per data point.

approximately by half upon increasing N_v from 1 to 4, and by half again upon a further increase to $N_v = 16$. This enhancement in accuracy may be understood in terms of the increase in the ion jump rate that results from the higher number of mobile defects. Consistent with previous results,³¹ these data indicate that the relative error in the tracer diffusion coefficient is governed by the number of particle jumps, rather than the simulation time itself.

In summary, the results of Figures 4, 5, and 6 clearly show how simulation time, cell size, and defect concentration determine the accuracy of a calculated diffusion coefficient. Taken together, the results also show that a description of the error solely in terms of t_{sim} will not capture the dependence on N_O , and vice versa. Hence, a quantity is required that is related to these parameters, and consideration of our data suggests that the key quantity that determines the error is the number of tracer particles that have jumped at least once. Specifically, analysis of the kMC simulation data (e.g., Figure 4) reveals that, at relatively short t_{sim} , most tracer particles have not jumped yet, while, in the plateau at relatively long t_{sim} , most tracer particles have jumped at least once (for a detailed analysis see Section S3 in Data S1). Instead of tracking individual particle jumps, the question of whether or not most tracer particles have jumped at least once can be easily answered by considering the effective number of jumps per particle, $\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2$. The extreme case $\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2 \gg 1$ corresponds to the plateau with respect to t_{sim} (Figure 4). The other extreme case, $\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2 \ll 1$, corresponds to the plateau with respect to N_O (Figure 5).

4.3 | Estimator for the relative error of the diffusion coefficient

In the previous Section, we identified $\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2$, the effective number of jumps per k tracer particle, as a simple indicator of whether a simulation run falls in either of the plateaus of the relative error, with respect to t_{sim} or N_k . We also established that, at long simulation

times, the trend of the relative error approaches the closed-form expression for an ensemble of ordinary random walkers (Equations 9 and 10). At shorter simulation times, on the other hand, the relative error is substantially larger than predicted by Equation (9); this is readily understood by considering that, in this case, a large portion of the tracer particles will not have jumped at all. Actually, these particles will not, on principle, have been able to jump, because they were never approached by a vacancy—hence, they cannot be conceived as random walkers, and they are irrelevant with regard to the error in D_k^* . As stated in the previous Section, we will, therefore, focus on the number of particles that have jumped at least once.

To derive an estimator for this number, we consider the effective number of jumps as a total count, rather than an average per particle. The (total) effective number of jumps, $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}$, is given by

$$N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} = N_k \cdot \frac{\langle r_k^2 \rangle}{s_k^2}. \quad (11)$$

Note that the effective number of jumps will generally differ from the true number of jumps by the tracer correlation factor f^* .

We denote by \mathbb{J} the set of tracer particles that have jumped at least once, and by $N_k^{\mathbb{J}}$ the number of these particles. Over the course of a simulation, $N_k^{\mathbb{J}}$ increases and, clearly, the number of particles that have not yet jumped decreases. As a consequence, for a given jump, the probability that the jumping particle jumps for the first time decreases, until it reaches 0 (once all particles have jumped). As a simple approximation, we model this differentially as

$$\frac{dN_k^{\mathbb{J}}}{dN_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}} = -\frac{N_k - N_k^{\mathbb{J}}}{N_k}, \quad (12)$$

from which we obtain, by integration,

$$N_k^{\mathbb{J}} = N_k \cdot \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\langle r_k^2 \rangle}{s_k^2}\right) \right]. \quad (13)$$

In order to test the accuracy of Equation (13), we extracted the true values of $N_k^{\mathbb{J}}$ from a set of kMC simulations (see Figure S2 and Video in Data S1), and found that Equation (13) is accurate to within the natural scatter of the kMC runs.

Bearing in mind that, in the long-time limit, the relative error in $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ should correspond to Equation (10), we make the assumption that this same expression applies generally to the tracer particles in subset \mathbb{J} , with N being substituted by $N_k^{\mathbb{J}}$. Combining in this way Equations (10) and (13), we obtain our closed-form expression for the relative error in D_k^* :

$$u_{\text{rel}} = \frac{u(D_k^*)}{D_k^*} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{d \cdot N_k \cdot \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\langle r_k^2 \rangle}{s_k^2}\right) \right]}}. \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) quantitatively incorporates all the characteristics that were identified previously in Section 4.2. For sufficiently short

FIGURE 7 Relative errors in the tracer diffusion coefficient, D_k^* , as a function of (A) our estimator N_k^j , dash-dotted line, Equation (14); (B) $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}$, dotted line, Equation (15); and (C) N_k , dashed line, Equation (16). The relative errors were calculated from the standard deviations of 100 kMC runs per parameter set; for different crystal structures, over a wide range of temperatures, cell sizes, and numbers of vacancies.

simulation times (that is, when most particles have not jumped yet, and one has $\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2 \ll 1$), the term in square bracket becomes $\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2$ {because $1 - \exp(-x) \approx x$ for small x }, and hence, Equation (14) simplifies to

$$u_{\text{rel}} \approx \sqrt{\frac{2}{d \cdot N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}}}. \quad (15)$$

This essentially amounts to an inverse-square-root dependence of the relative error on the simulation time. For sufficiently long simulation times ($\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2 \gg 1$), in contrast, Equation (14) yields, as required (cf. Equation 9), the limiting case of the inverse-square-root dependence on the number of mobile particles:

$$u_{\text{rel}} \approx \sqrt{\frac{2}{d \cdot N_k}}. \quad (16)$$

In other words, this limiting case tells us that, even for infinite simulation time, the relative error can only reach a finite limit that is prescribed by the number of tracer particles in the cell.

Having obtained Equation (14), we subjected it to scrutiny by analyzing the relative error in D_k^* for various crystal structures. Beside our model perovskite SrTiO_3 , kMC simulations were carried out on supercells of the 3-dimensional simple cubic (sc), face-centered cubic (fcc), and body-centered cubic (bcc) lattices, and of the 2-dimensional square lattice. In all cases, we find, as shown in Figure 7A, good agreement between the observed relative errors and the predictions of Equation (14). Clearly, $u_{\text{rel}}(D_k^*)$ cannot be estimated from either $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}$ or N_k alone, but both quantities impose lower bounds upon u_{rel} (Equations (15) and (16)), as indicated by the dotted/dashed lines in Figure 7B,C. In that regard, Equation (16) is particularly useful because it yields a lower bound without any prior knowledge of the ion transport kinetics. For example, for a three-dimensional lattice with 100 tracer particles, Equation (16) indicates that the relative uncertainty in D_k^* from a single MD run will at best be $\approx 8\%$ (but typically larger, for

finite t_{sim}). To achieve 1% precision with a single MD run, the simulation cell must contain at least $\frac{2}{3} \cdot 10^4 \approx 6667$ particles, provided that the plateau with respect to t_{sim} is reached, i.e., $\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2 \gg 1$. In view of current computational capabilities, the requirement of simulating a cell with $\sim 10^4$ particles implies that, in AIMD, this degree of precision in D_k^* cannot realistically be obtained from a single simulation, but only by calculating an average over multiple independent runs (e.g., given a cell with 250 tracer particles, at least 25 independent runs would be necessary; see Section S4 in Data S1).

We close this Section with two important points. Since the kMC data that we produced (shown in Figure 7) were restricted to the range $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} > 2$, our expression is restricted to this range of $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}$. However, the use of our expression below $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} \approx 3$ is strongly discouraged because, at this point, the relative error surpasses 50%. The problem is that, taking the absolute error (σ) to estimate a 2σ interval, within which the majority ($\approx 95\%$) of possible outcomes fall, yields for $u_{\text{rel}} > 50\%$ values of D_k^* in the 2σ interval that are negative. Consequently a lower bound to the order of magnitude of D_k^* cannot be estimated. Thus, $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} \approx 3$ represents for us a natural lower boundary.

5 | APPLICATION OF THE CLOSED-FORM EXPRESSION TO MD RESULTS

In the first part of this Section, we examine how well Equation (14) performs in calculating the error in a tracer diffusion coefficient obtained from an MD simulation. To this end, we produce and analyze MD diffusion data for oxygen diffusion in SrTiO_3 , with the (N_0, T, t_{sim}) conditions ranging from those characteristic of AIMD to those achievable with classical MD. In addition, we demonstrate the usefulness of Equation (14) for planning and optimizing the distribution of computational resources for MD simulations. In the second part of this Section, we examine two datasets from the literature in order to emphasize how our expression can be used to assess whether simulation results are sufficiently precise to deduce sound conclusions.

FIGURE 8 Mean squared displacements of oxide ions, $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$, from three independent MD simulations for each set of (N_O, N_V, T) conditions. (A) and (B) $3 \times 3 \times 3$ supercell with $N_O = 80$ and $N_V = 1$ at $T = 1200\text{K}$; (C) and (D) $3 \times 3 \times 3$ supercell with $N_O = 80$ and $N_V = 1$ at $T = 2000\text{K}$; (E) $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercell with $N_O = 374$ and $N_V = 1$ at $T = 2000\text{K}$; (F) $20 \times 20 \times 20$ supercell with $N_O = 23976$ and $N_V = 24$ at $T = 2000\text{K}$.

5.1 | The influence of cell size, simulation time, and temperature

MD runs with different t_{sim} were obtained by extracting sections of the respective duration from nanosecond-long simulations. For every set of (N_O, T, t_{sim}) conditions, three independent runs were carried out; the scatter in D_O^* was estimated from the empirical standard deviation of the three extracted values of D_O^* . As shown in Figure 8, we found good agreement between the observed scatter in D_O^* and the prediction in all considered cases.

The first case we considered is a supercell of $3 \times 3 \times 3$ SrTiO₃ unit cells, with one oxygen vacancy (i.e., Sr₂₇Ti₂₇O₈₀), run for 25ps. Such conditions ($N_O = 80, t_{\text{sim}} = 25\text{ps}$) are characteristic of AIMD simulations. At $T = 1200\text{K}$ (Figure 8A), the observed number of jumps is so small that individual jumps become apparent as steps in the $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$ curve (note that such steps may not be discernible if time averaging is applied for the calculation of $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$). From the final value of $\langle r_O^2 \rangle$, it may be deduced with Equation (11) that, for one of the three runs, the total effective number of jumps is smaller than one; this indicates that, in this case, the finite value of $\langle r_O^2 \rangle$ is due only to vibrational displacements. Clearly, in this case, t_{sim} is too short. The estimate of

$N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} \approx 1$ also indicates that the simulation run should be extended at least by a factor of 10 (to $t_{\text{sim}} = 250\text{ps}$) to obtain an effective number of jumps well above the critical limit of $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} = 3$, as demonstrated in Figure 8B: for this much longer run, we found $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} \approx 15$, and thus, it is reasonable to extract a value of D_O^* from the $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$ curve. In cases where it is not computationally feasible to extend t_{sim} sufficiently (i.e., such that $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} \geq 3$), the results should be discarded. Note also that, even with $t_{\text{sim}} = 250\text{ps}$, the simulations at $T = 1200\text{K}$ are still subject to a considerable scatter ($\approx 20\%$) in D_O^* .

As was pointed out before, the simulation time that is necessary to obtain reliable jump statistics depends on the temperature. This becomes evident by considering that the 25ps runs at $T = 2000\text{K}$ (Figure 8C) display a relative error close to that of the 250ps runs at $T = 1200\text{K}$ (Figure 8B). Extending the MD runs at $T = 2000\text{K}$ to $t_{\text{sim}} = 250\text{ps}$, the agreement of the $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(t)$ curves is visibly better than previously, as shown in Figure 8D. This is reflected in the lower relative error in D_O^* (observed and predicted) of ca. 10%. A further increase of t_{sim} , however, will not result in a further improvement. From the final value of $\langle r_O^2 \rangle(250\text{ps}) \approx 15\text{\AA}^2$, the estimated effective number of jumps per tracer particle is ≈ 1.9 (Equation 11); being greater than unity, this indicates that the relative error should already

FIGURE 9 $D_{\text{Li}}^*(T)$ data from AIMD simulations in Ref. 62 for Li_3OBr (A); Li_3OCl (B); $\text{Li}_3\text{OCl}_{0.5}\text{Br}_{0.5}$ (C). Errors in D_{Li}^* were estimated from Equation (14), minimum/maximum-slope Arrhenius fits are shown as dotted lines, linear regression fits are shown as dashed lines; (D) estimated intervals of uncertainty in D_{Li}^* at 300K, obtained by an extrapolation of the Arrhenius fits with minimum/maximum slope.

be close to its plateau value. Indeed, Equation (16) predicts a lower bound of $\approx 9\%$ for the relative error. As a consequence, it would be advantageous to calculate an average from several independent runs (see Section S4 in Data S1), rather than to extend the simulation time: for example, the average of the three independent results shown in Figure 8D is expected to be accurate to within $\approx 6\%$, and, with that, more accurate than a single run with $t_{\text{sim}} \rightarrow \infty$.

Another way to decrease u_{rel} is to increase the cell size and thus the number N_{O} of oxygen tracer particles. The next case, Figure 8E, refers to a simulation of a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercell run for 250ps, that is, at the limit of AIMD simulations. Compared to the runs with the same t_{sim} in the smaller supercell, the results are more accurate, with $u_{\text{rel}} \approx 5\%$. Again, consideration of Equation (16) indicates that extending t_{sim} could at best lead to a further decrease in u_{rel} to $\approx 4\%$.

If a relative error below 1% is required for each simulated value of D_k^* —and this may be the case if a value of D_k^* with an error less than one order of magnitude is to be predicted through extrapolation over several hundred Kelvin—the cell size and simulation time must be sufficiently large. From Equation (16), we discern that sufficiently large means that the supercell must contain at least $\frac{2}{3} \cdot 10^4$ tracer particles. These criteria are met in Figure 8F, with a $20 \times 20 \times 20$ supercell and $t_{\text{sim}} = 750\text{ps}$; the number of vacancies could be increased to 24, yielding excellent jump statistics without additional computational cost, while remaining below the limit of 1% defect concentration, above which undesirable defect-defect interactions are assumed to become relevant. In supercells of usual size in AIMD simulations, that is, a few tens to hundreds of particles, any number of vacancies above 1 will correspond to a concentration above this limit.

5.2 | Ab-initio MD: Literature examples

As a first example, we consider an AIMD study⁵³ of our model system (oxygen diffusion by a vacancy mechanism in SrTiO_3): from the relevant simulation parameters ($N_{\text{O}} = 189$, $t_{\text{sim}} = 10\text{ps}$) and a lattice parameter

of $\approx 4\text{\AA}$, we estimate the effective number of jumps, $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}$ from the given diffusion coefficients D_{O}^* , by combining Equations (1) and (11):

$$N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} = \frac{6t_{\text{sim}}D_{\text{O}}^*N_{\text{O}}}{s_{\text{V}}^2}. \quad (17)$$

Only one of the data points corresponds to a value of $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}}$ above the critical limit of 3; most notably, the data point at the lowest temperature ($T = 1000\text{K}$) corresponds to $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} < 1$, possibly indicating a non-diffusive origin of $\langle r_{\text{O}}^2 \rangle$. Hence, there is no evidence that the low activation enthalpy (of 0.30eV) reported by the authors is more than a simulation artifact (caused by short simulation times and a small supercell). A more general conclusion is that, although AIMD contains more chemical information on a system, it may yield a physically less accurate result than force-field MD.

As a second example, we consider an AIMD study⁶² of the Li-ion-conducting antiperovskites Li_3OCl , Li_3OBr , and $\text{Li}_3\text{OCl}_{0.5}\text{Br}_{0.5}$. From the values of $D_{\text{Li}}^*(T)$ obtained for the temperature range $750 \leq T/\text{K} \leq 2000$, the authors calculated low-temperature conductivities by extrapolating to $T = 300\text{K}$, and pointed out that the extracted 2:1 ratio of the conductivities of $\text{Li}_3\text{OCl}_{0.5}\text{Br}_{0.5}$ and Li_3OCl matches the corresponding ratio of conductivities found in experiment. To assess the reliability of this extrapolation, we calculated the relative errors of the reported values of D_{Li}^* with Equation (14), from the reported $\langle r_{\text{Li}}^2 \rangle$ values at $t = t_{\text{sim}}$. It was verified that all data points fulfilled the condition $N_{\text{jumps}}^{\text{eff}} \geq 3$. Hence, 2σ -intervals could be estimated with the relative error obtained from Equation (14). On this basis, linear fits with minimum and maximum slopes were constructed, as shown in Figure 9.

An extrapolation of our minimum/maximum slope estimates to 300K yields, in all three cases, a range of values that spans over more than two orders of magnitude. Given this huge uncertainty, it cannot be judged whether a simulation at 300K would indeed produce a higher conductivity of $\text{Li}_3\text{OCl}_{0.5}\text{Br}_{0.5}$ than of Li_3OCl or the opposite. The seemingly precise matching of the reported conductivity ratio

with the experimental value (2:1) is, therefore, likely to be a coincidence.

6 | CONCLUDING REMARKS

If one has performed an MD simulation of solid-state diffusion, confirmed that the cell has equilibrated, and observed that $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$, the mean squared displacement of species k , has increased with time, it may seem that the difficult part has been completed. All that is left is to calculate the tracer diffusion coefficient of k . Our study reveals that, even then, much remains to be done.

In the first part of this study, we examined the behavior of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curves, and discovered two highly counter-intuitive features: first, calculating time-averaged mean squared displacement curves does not increase the precision of the extracted diffusion coefficient, even though it suggests, by virtue of producing curves of a very smooth appearance, a higher degree of precision. Second, obtaining the diffusion coefficient by means of least-squares linear regression from the $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$ curve yields results that are no more precise than those obtained by a simple difference quotient. While in both cases, the considered methods were found to be equivalent with regard to the uncertainty in the diffusion coefficient, there may be other reasons to prefer one approach over the other. Since time averaging may mask statistically and physically questionable results, we contend that the simple ensemble average (Equation 6) should always be inspected. Also, we argue in favor of using a difference quotient for the calculation of a diffusion coefficient, rather than linear regression, in order to avoid mistaking the standard error of the linear regression slope for a measure of the uncertainty in D_k^* .

In the second part of this study, we focused specifically on the error associated with the tracer diffusion coefficient, D_k^* , obtained from the analysis of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle(t)$. A simple closed-form expression is proposed that allows the relative error in D_k^* to be estimated from the final $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$ value of the simulation run. This expression, furthermore, is instructive in that it indicates the plateaus of the statistical error in D_k^* : the smaller the cell, the sooner a plateau of the statistical error will be reached for increasing simulation times. For very small simulation times, on the other hand, the beneficial effect of increasing the cell size vanishes.

Finally, we highlight three points that will help researchers to obtain statistically meaningful tracer diffusion coefficients from MD simulations:

1. The relative error in a tracer diffusion coefficient, D_k^* , calculated from an MD run, may easily be estimated with Equation (14) from the final value of $\langle r_k^2 \rangle$.
2. The relative error $u_{\text{rel}}(D_k^*)$ may be reduced by extending the simulation time, until it approaches a plateau once the effective number of jumps per particle exceeds unity ($\langle r_k^2 \rangle / s_k^2 > 1$). In that regime, it is advisable to increase the cell size or to average over a number of independent runs, rather than to extend the simulation run time further.
3. The number of tracer particles in the cell, N_k , prescribes the lower bound of the relative error (Equation 16), for $t_{\text{sim}} \rightarrow \infty$. For a single run to generate values of D_k^* within 10% precision, it follows that at least 67 mobile particles are necessary. For results within 1% precision, the number of mobile particles must exceed 6666.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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